

Netherlands Food and Consumer
Product Safety Authority
Ministry of Agriculture,
Nature and Food Quality

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To the Head of Agency of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority

Advice of the Director of the Office for Risk Assessment & Research

Advice on the implementation of the National Residues Plan: supplementary advice on not previously classified substances: supplementary

Office for Risk Assessment & Research

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Background

The National Residues Plan (NPR) in products of animal origin is the Dutch elaboration of Directive 96/22/EC¹ and the former 96/23/EC². This Directive specifies which groups of substances the Member States are required to include in their annual monitoring of animal products. As such, the NPR is an important cornerstone for the free movement of animal products within the EU and for the export of animal products outside the EU. On 14 December 2019, Directive 96/23/EC will be repealed and replaced by Regulation EU 2017/625³. In addition to the specified compulsory controls, this new regulation offers more space for additional risk-based controls by the Member States.

In 2017, the Office for Risk Assessment and Research (BuRO) commissioned WFSR⁴ to develop an approach that can be used to structure the NPR in a risk-oriented manner. There are different ways of prioritising possible (chemical) food safety risks. A quantitative analysis of individual substances requires both time and budget, which are often only available to a limited extent (van Asselt et al., 2013; van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2015; Van der Fels-Klerx et al., 2018). Decision trees or expert judgement appear to be the best alternatives for prioritising (chemical) substances with regard to food safety risks; this provides sufficient differentiation between substances on the basis of available data. For the prioritisation of substances, WFSR designed decision trees according to which substances can be classified with a high, medium or low priority (van Asselt et al., 2018a; van Asselt et al., 2018b). The classification is carried out on the basis of risks for food safety (probability x effect). The criteria are reproduced in table 1.

¹ Council Directive 96/22/EC of 29 April 1996 concerning the prohibition on the use in livestock farming of certain substances having a hormonal or thyreostatic action and of β -agonists, and repealing Directives 81/602/EEC, 88/146/EEC and 88/299/EEC.

² Council Directive 96/23/EC on measures to monitor certain substances and residues thereof in live animals and animal products and repealing Directives 85/358/EEC and 86/469/EEC and Decisions 89/187/EEC and 91/664/EEC.

³ Regulation (EU) 2017/625 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products, amending Regulations (EC) No 999/2001, (EC) No 396/2005, (EC) No 1069/2009, (EC) No 1107/2009, (EU) No 1151/2012, (EU) No 652/2014, (EU) 2016/429 and (EU) 2016/2031 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Regulations (EC) No 1/2005 and (EC) No 1099/2009 and Council Directives 98/58/EC, 1999/74/EC, 2007/43/EC, 2008/119/EC and 2008/120/EC, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 854/2004 and (EC) No 882/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Directives 89/608/EEC, 89/662/EEC, 90/425/EEC, 91/496/EEC, 96/23/EC, 96/93/EC and 97/78/EC and Council Decision 92/438/EEC (Official Controls Regulation).

⁴ Wageningen Food Safety Research, up to 1-6-2019 RIKILT

The accompanying decision trees can be found in annex 1. Unlike previous sets of advice, in this advice only decision tree I and decision tree III are used. Substances classified with high priority deserve more attention within the monitoring programme than substances classified medium or low. Over the past few years, BuRO has already advised the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) on the structure of the NPR and on the layout of the monitoring (BuRO, 2018;2019;2020).

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Table 1. Criteria in decision trees that are used to classify substances on the basis of food safety risks.

Criteria used in the decision trees	Group I prohibited substances	Group III authorised veterinary medicinal products
Is there an action limit, MRL/ML ⁵ ?		X
Limit exceeded in the last 5 years	X	X
Use (or probability thereof)	X	X
Scientific information about risks to humans	X	
Length of waiting period		X
Limit exceeded in animal feed in the last 5 years		
Transfer of substance to animal product		
Essential for human application?		X

In response to the WFSR study and the BuRO advice and in advance of the coming into effect of Regulation (EU) 2017/625, the National Residues Plan working group of the NVWA asked BuRO to "issue advice on how the NPR can be restructured in a risk-oriented manner, taking into account the space afforded by the new Official Control Regulation (EU) 2017/625 and the previously issued advice by RIKILT⁶." In 2019, BuRO first published an advice in which the above question was answered (BuRO, 2019) Further advice followed in 2020 (BuRO, 2020). In the current advice, the remaining substance groups from the Implementing Regulation (i.e. SANTE 11987-2017 Rev 9) have been classified that were not included in previous sets of advice. The Implementing Regulation for the control of residues of relevant substances as referred to in article 19 section 3a and 3b of Regulation (EU) 2017/625 will replace the appendices to Directive 96/23/EC.

Tables 2 and 3 provide an overview of substance groups and animals/animal products addressed in the previous sets of advice and the current advice or relating to current studies.

⁵ Statutory limit for levels in food products. MRL: Maximum Residue Limit for residues of veterinary medicinal products; ML: Maximum Limit for environmental contaminants.

⁶ RIKILT merged (on 1-6-2019) with the Laboratory for Feed and Food Safety of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) under the name [Wageningen Food Safety Research](#) (WFSR).

Findings

- Figures 1 to 4 provide an overview per substance group of the number of substances classified low, medium or high for cattle, milk, pig, horse, goat, sheep, poultry and egg (for the classification of all individual substances see the underlying report from WFSR (van Asselt et al., 2020)). For a number of substances (Figure 4), it is concluded that a survey into the use of the substances is needed, before classification is possible.

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Figure 1. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group A1 (substances with a hormonal or thyreostatic effect and beta-agonists, use of which is prohibited according to Directive 96/22/EC; stilbenes (A1a), antithyroid substances (A1b), steroids (A1c), resorcylic acid lactones (A1d), beta-agonists (A1e)).

High #1: means that use of the substances is unknown. No products registered by the FDA (U.S. Food & Drug Administration) or EU registrations for farm animals were identified. However, products on the basis of the substances in question were found on the Internet.

High #2: means that use of the substances is unknown. However, products registered by the FDA or EU farm animal registrations were found on the basis of the substances in question. However, use in the animal type in question is not very probable.

Figure 2. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group A2 (prohibited substances as included in table 2 of the appendix to Regulation (EU) no. 37/2010⁷).

High #1: means that use of the substances is unknown. No products registered by the FDA (U.S. Food & Drug Administration) or EU registrations for farm animals were identified. However, products on the basis of the substances in questions were found on the Internet.

⁷ Commission Regulation (EU) no. 37/2010 on pharmacologically active substances and their classification based on maximum residue limits in foodstuffs of animal origin.

Figure 3. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group A3 (pharmacological active substances not included in table 1 of the appendix to Regulation (EU) no. 37/2010 or not authorised according to Regulation (EC) no. 1831/2003⁸; not authorised pesticides (A3b), not authorised antimicrobial substances (A3c), not authorised coccidiostats and histomonostats (A3d), protein and peptide hormones (A3e), not authorised sedatives (A3f)).

High #1: means that use of the substances is unknown. No products registered by the FDA (U.S. Food & Drug Administration) or EU registrations for farm animals were identified. However, products on the basis of the substances in question were found on the Internet.

High #2: means that use of the substances is unknown. However, products registered by the FDA or EU farm animal registrations were found on the basis of the substances in question. However, use in the animal type in question is not very probable.

⁸ Regulation (EC) no. 1831/2003 on additives for use in animal nutrition.

Figure 4. An overview of the number of low, medium or high classified substances from group B (pharmacologically active substances authorised for the use in food-producing animals according to EU legislation; authorised insecticides (B1b), authorised sedatives (B1c), other authorised substances (B1e), authorised coccidiostats and histomonostats (B2)).

Start survey*1 means that a substance is not at present included in the national residues control plan but that it can be concluded from sales data that agents containing these substances are sold in considerable quantities⁹. A survey into the use of this substance in this animal type is recommended.

Start survey*2 means that a substance is not currently included in the national residues control plan, but that non-compliant results have been identified in related animal types. A survey into the use of this substance in this animal type is recommended.

⁹ In this context, threshold values are employed of at least 10, 65 or 150 kg per year, depending on the substances and/or animal type (Van Asselt et al., 2020a).

Findings (continued)

- Generally speaking, there are missing datasets for the investigated animal types/animal products. This results in an 'unknown' route in the decision tree. Causes of missing and/or incomplete datasets:
 - Limited (n<10/year) or no monitoring data.
 - Sales details for the veterinary medicinal products could almost entirely not be specified according to the evaluated animal types because these veterinary medicinal products generally have a registration for multiple animal types.
 - EFSA monitoring data relating to residues of veterinary medicinal products sheep and goat make no distinction between the two animal types.
- A lack of monitoring data and lack of insight into use means that certain substances are given a high classification according to the principle of prevention. For non-authorised substances (group A), this is indicated as high#1 or high#2 in figures 1 to 3. For the group of authorised substances (group B), the lack of data leads to the conclusion that information about the use of the substance group in question is still missing (start survey, figure 4).
- In certain cases, for example in the case of corticosteroids, milk is missing as an analysis matrix. For the other substance groups, there are no indications that the analysis matrix needs to be changed.
- Not all classified substances from group A are at present included in the current monitoring programmes. A number of the substances from group A3b (insecticides) and A3c (antimicrobial agents) are however used on farm animals outside the EU, which may result in the presence of residues in imported foodstuffs.
- In the current monitoring within the EU, the emphasis is on substances of which residues have been found in the past or which are known to be used. On the other hand, the WFSR investigation suggests that the current selection of substances (group A and B) is too limited. Certainly with regard to the monitoring of animals/animal products from third countries (import).

Answer to the question

How can the NPR be restructured in a risk-oriented manner, taking into account the space afforded by the new Official Control Regulation (EU) 2017/625 and the previously issued advice by RIKILT?

The tables drawn up by WFSR with low, medium or high classification can be used for a risk-oriented choice of substances for the structuring of the NPR by the directorate Inspection of the NVWA.

The NPR can be structured in a risk-oriented manner, in respect of choice of substances, by opting for chemical substance-animal or chemical substance-animal product combinations classified by WFSR as high and medium. For the classification of all individual substances, see Van Asselt et al., 2020a.

Advice from BuRO

To the Head of Agency

- Use the classification of chemical substance-animal or chemical substance-animal product combinations as reported in this advice for a risk-oriented substance choice in structuring the NPR. Pay specific attention to imported products.
- Also make a classification for all substance groups animal/animal product combinations specified for the NPR, so that a risk-oriented choice can also be made for all substances for monitoring in the other animal types/animal products.
- Evaluate the classification of the substance animal/animal product combinations regularly.

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- Focus on making structural agreements with FIDIN and SDa in the field of data interchange.

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Yours sincerely,

Office for Risk Assessment & Research
Prof. Antoon Opperhuizen

Appendix 1. Decision trees

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Group I - Prohibited substances

Decision tree (prohibited substances) relating to table 1 in which the criteria for the classification of substances are included.

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Group III - Authorised substances EU

Decision tree (authorised veterinary medicinal products) relating to table 1 in which the criteria for the classification of substances are included.

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